

Endogamous Marriage Among Santeri in the Sociological Perspective of Islamic Law

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Abstract: Endogamous marriage among students at Pesantren al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor has become the focus of attention in this study. This study aims to understand the purpose and implications of the practice of endogamous marriage in the context of the pesantren, by exploring the perspective of the sociology of Islamic law. This field research examines the application of laws in social life. It uses a sociological approach of Islamic law to reveal facts about endogamous marriage among santri at pesantren al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman, Parung Bogor, Indonesia. Through a qualitative approach, data were collected through interviews with students, kyai, and pesantren staff, as well as related literature studies. The results showed that the practice of endogamous marriage in pesantren aims to preserve, maintain, and strengthen harmonious relationships among fellow students, while strengthening the values taught in pesantren. This is also seen as an effort to maintain the identity of the pesantren and ensure the continuity of the generation of santri who continue to inherit the values of the pesantren. From the perspective of Islamic law, endogamous marriages are considered in accordance with the principle of *kafā'ah*, which emphasizes conformity or equality between spouses in various aspects of life. Thus, this practice is not only part of the pesantren culture, but also an effort to maintain the integrity and sustainability of the student community. This research provides a deeper understanding of the importance of endogamous marriage practices in the context of pesantren, as well as its impact in maintaining pesantren values and strengthening the identity of the santri community.

Keywords: Endogami Marriage, Santeri, *Kafā'ah*, Sociology of Islamic Law

1. Introduction

The practice of endogamous marriage among santeri in Parung District, Bogor Regency has unique characteristics compared to other regions in Indonesia. The leader of the pesantren has stipulated that the wedding program is only available to the santeri, not to those outside the pesantren, and is held once every year and has been running for decades.

Endogamous marriages generally require individuals to find a spouse in the same social environment as them, such as in the same family, social, or residential environment.(Almeida et al., 2023) Fauzan explained that this is a marriage between individuals from tribes, clans, clans, or kinships who are in the same environment. Typically, this practice is done to preserve wealth within the community, strengthen the group's defenses from potential outside threats, defend lineages, or for other exclusive reasons.(Fauzan et al., 2023)

The motives behind the practice of endogamous marriage vary widely. Among them is to create a harmonious family because it departs from many similarities, such as the same sociological background and education level, which are both born from one womb of pesantren.(Almeida et al., 2023) By marrying in the same environment, the family's vision and mission can remain and tend to be easier to maintain and maintain, thus strengthening family harmony and economic stability.(Muhsin, 2020) In addition, endogamous marriage can also be used as a strategy to strengthen the group's defenses from potential outside threats.(Hidayatullah, 2022) By bonding within the same community, groups can work together to face challenges and keep their environment safe and stable.(Hasanah, 2023)

In addition, the practice of endogamous marriage can also maintain lineage and strengthen familial relationships.(Utomo & McDonald, 2021) By marrying in the same environment, kinship between individuals can be well maintained, and it is possible to maintain family traditions and customs that have existed for a long time.(Lusiana Magho et al., 2023) Other exclusive reasons could include attempts to maintain certain privileges or power within the group.(Alasdaq & Irawan, 2023) Thus, endogamous marriage among santeri is a practice that reflects the close relationship between individuals in a community. Not only does this impact on a personal level, but also has far-reaching implications for the stability and identity of the group.

Unfortunately, until now there is still very little research related to endogamous marriage among santeri, even though there are many pesantren in Indonesia. Several studies have been conducted in several regions in Indonesia such as Madura,(Hanafi,

2021) Karangasem,(Baskara et al., 2021) Pegringsingan,(Nursanti et al., 2023) Bangil,(Fauzan et al., 2023) Where the practice of endogamous marriage is not limited to santeri. The peculiarity of this phenomenon lies in the fact that the practice of endogamous marriage in such areas involves other communities outside the santeri circle. Research related to endogamous marriage among students needs to be done because it can provide information on how marriage among students in Islamic boarding schools can maintain harmony in the family than non-santeri. In addition, the findings obtained can be the basis of development research conducted in understanding endogamous marriage in society. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to find out how endogamous marriage among santeri can have a positive impact in the perspective of culture and sociology of Islamic law.

2. Method

This research is a field research that uses data collection techniques in the form of interviews and literature searches that include relevant scientific books and journals.(Benuf et al., 2019) The informants involved in this study consisted of twenty people, including Islamic boarding school administrators, university leaders, marriage committees, female alumni, and female students from al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Islamic boarding school, Parung Bogor. In determining informants, purposive sampling techniques are used to ensure that the data obtained is more accurate and on target. The informant's criteria include (1) understanding of the concept of endogamous marriage; (2) experience in observing the series of endogamous marriages among santeri, and (3) status as an alumnus of santeri from pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman, Parung Bogor.

The approach used in this study is a sociological juridical approach because of its focus on legal studies that look at social reality. This approach aims to find and describe facts related to the practice of endogamy among the students of pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman, Parung Bogor. Data analysis techniques used include various stages such as data reduction, presentation, and conclusions. In addition, the data validity technique applied in this study is source triangulation, which is by comparing data obtained from several sources or informants.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 *Kafā'ah* as the Main Reason for Endogamous Marriage Among Santeri and Its Stages

To achieve the purpose of marriage easily, it is imperative that the marriage is built on a solid foundation, one of which is the existence of *kafā'ah* between husband and wife. (Hafidzi et al., 2020) *Kafā'ah* refers to comfort, equality, and compatibility between the two parties. This implies that the men and women who will form a household must be balanced in all respects. (Munir, 2023)

Furthermore, the concept of *kafā'ah* suggests that a husband is equal to his wife, meaning they have an equal and commensurate position in terms of social, moral, and economic levels. (Abdul Hadi Ismail, 2020) According to Zainal Arifin Haji Munir's view, marriage based on the principle of *kafā'ah* is an important factor that can encourage the happiness of married couples, as well as provide assurance for women's safety from potential failure or chaos in the household. (Munir, 2023) With a more equal balance between husband and wife, success in married life can be more guaranteed and more protected from all losses. (Syafi'i, 2020)

However, it should be noted that *kafā'ah* is not an absolute requirement that must be met in order to consummate a marriage. (Qodariah Barkah, 2020) Meskipun demikian, wali pernikahan (*wali*) memiliki kekuasaan untuk rejected the proposal of a man who was considered unworthy (*kufū'*) of his daughter. (Indrayanto, 2023) However, according to a stronger view, *kafā'ah* only takes place in the context of faith and religion, such as adherence to Islam or one's good and bad qualities. (Iim et al., 2022) There is a difference of opinion among scholars as to whether *kafā'ah* is one of the legal requirements of marriage. (Suwarjin, 2022)

The first opinion, held by most imams of the madhhab including Abu Haneefah, Malik, and As-Shāfi'i, asserts that *kafā'ah* is considered important in maintaining the continuation of the marriage, although it is not an absolute legal requirement. (Putri, n.d.) They argue that *kafā'ah* has an important value in maintaining the continuity of the marriage relationship. Meanwhile, the second opinion held by Imam Ahmad, Ats-Tsauri, and some Hanafi scholars, argues that *kafā'ah* is a legal requirement that must be fulfilled in marriage. They argue that *kafā'ah* should be taken into account directly in the marriage process to ensure the harmony and continuity of the conjugal relationship. (Abdul Gofur, 2022)

Among the students of al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Islamic boarding school, Parung Bogor, the term *kafā'ah* is also well known. Santri refers to individuals who attend Islamic religious education in pesantren as santri. They are students studying in religious educational institutions headed by a Kiai. Santri generally pursue education that emphasizes traditional or orthodox Islamic teachings, often in neighborhoods far from their parents, because pesantren are usually located in separate places from public settlements.

In applying the concept of *kafā'ah* among students in Parung Bogor, they argue that it is one of the important pillars in marriage. Some of them state that *kafā'ah* is not only related to nasab and economic aspects, but can also apply in matters such as kyai similarity, education, fate, eating habits, and living conditions while studying in pesantren. The results of interviews with the students reinforced this understanding.

Subaikhi Ikhwan says:

Students and female students who marry at pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman do not experience discrimination based on their social strata, both in economic and social terms. In this pesantren, there is no separation or assessment based on social strata. All students are united in the understanding that they are both students who come with the aim of learning and following the teachings of Islam.¹

Khaeruddin also said:

Pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman emphasizes equality and brotherhood among its students, regardless of their social or economic background. All students are expected to follow the instructions and teachings of their teachers in the hope of gaining useful knowledge and a blessed life. Thus, the marriage process in this pesantren is based on equality and brotherhood among the students, regardless of differences in social strata.²

Furthermore, Ali Mutakin mentioned the following:

These students and female students are married without any element of coercion. The process of introducing and meeting couples is carried out through a ta'aruf process organized by the mass marriage committee from the Islamic Boarding School. This procedure requires both couples who will marry meet several

¹ Interview with Subaikhi Ikhwan, Daily Administrator of pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor, 2024.

² Interview with Khaeruddin, Daily Administrator of pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor, 2024.

requirements, including having completed undergraduate education for both parties and reaching age maturity, namely men at least 25 years old and women at least 20 years old.³

Similarly, Ghufron Maksun also said:

There is no element of coercion in this marriage process. Married couples are united according to their own wishes in choosing a life partner through a ta'aruf process that is carried out fairly and transparently. This process provides an opportunity for both parties to get to know each other and choose a partner who matches their desires and values.⁴

Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted, it is seen that one of the main reasons for endogamous marriages among santri is to get blessings from their teachers and to live a happy family life, *sakinah*, *mawaddah*, and *warahmah*. This is due to the similarity of personality and education possessed by couples who come from the same *pesantren* environment.

Although in Islamic law, a marriage is considered valid if it meets certain requirements and pillars, there are also other rules that require the concept of *kafā'ah* or equality between a man and a woman in various aspects. (Santoso et al., 2022) This concept of *kafā'ah* includes compatibility between spouses in religious, moral, social, and economic terms. In the context of marriage among students, this equality can also refer to similarities in education and understanding of Islam.

Thus, although there are certain requirements that must be met for the validity of a marriage in Islam, the concept of *kafā'ah* is also an important consideration, especially in creating harmony and continuity of the marriage relationship. This shows the importance of equality and harmony between couples, including in the context of education and religious understanding, in building a harmonious family life in Islamic teachings.

The concept of *kafā'ah* above is certainly very different from the concept of *kafā'ah* among nobles, especially those of *Alawite descent*. The *Alawites* and the nobility of the court had strict policies regarding marriage, in which they did not allow marriages outside their own sphere because they feared that their lineage would be cut off. Marriages outside their group were thought to result in the loss of royal blood or *Alawite* ancestry.

³ Interview with Ali Mutakin, Actor Endogamous marriage among students at al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor, 2024.

⁴ Interview with Ghufron Maksun, Committee of Endogamous Marriage among Students at al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

Therefore, they are very careful in choosing a life partner, and maintain the tradition of endogamous marriage. (Rusmini et al., 2023)

Although some consider the concept of *kafā'ah* to be a necessity (*luzūm al-'aqdī*), within Alawite circles there is an opportunity to choose a spouse among fellow *Alawites*. They may consider continuing endogamous marriages to maintain family traditions and lineage, or they may also waive those privileges if they cannot meet the requirements of the *kafā'ah*. Thus, there is flexibility in carrying out the tradition of endogamous marriage among the *Alawites*, depending on individual and family needs and conditions.

Endogamous marriages carried out among students at pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman, Parung Bogor, follow several stages that are almost the same as the stages of marriage in general. However, the difference lies in the steps taken, not in the substance or essence of the marriage process itself. This difference can be seen from the simple and concise series of endogamous wedding processions among students when compared to general weddings which often have many conditions and take longer. The cause of the endomy marriage process which tends to be shorter among students is claimed to be a form of Islamic teaching practice that is not burdensome in terms of marriage. This is reflected in the results of interviews which show that the marriage process among students is carried out efficiently and simply, without excessive burden.

The marriage among santri al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman follows the noble mandate of Habib Saggaf bin Mahdi BSA, the founder of this pesantren. The mandate states that in the case of marriage, it must not burden the students. The principle is to minimize the expenses that must be borne by students, who generally have mediocre living expenses. However, when they get married, they are sure that their needs will be provided for by Allah Almighty.⁵

The principles of marriage are still firmly held by the pesantren when they marry their santriwan and santriwati. Meanwhile, the stages of endogamy among students usually involve about eight steps, as shown in Figure 1 below.

⁵ Interview with Abdul Jalil, Daily Administrator of pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

Figure 1.

Stages of the Endogamous Marriage Process of Santri

Based on Figure 1 above, it can be known that santri endogamous marriage has 8 stages

First, the announcement of marriage; is the initial stage in the process of endogamy among students at the Al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Islamic boarding school in Bogor. At this stage, the pesantren announces to the guardians or students who have met the criteria for marriage. Generally, these announcements are made openly within the pesantren, either through social media, loudspeakers, announcements in public places, or through other means of communication available at the pesantren.⁶

Second, looking for data on prospective spouses; namely for students who are ready to get married will start looking for information about prospective partners who match the desired criteria. This information can be obtained through various ways, such as asking friends or elders in the pesantren, observing directly the interaction with potential partners, or asking for help from parties who are more experienced in marriage affairs in the pesantren environment.⁷

Third, make a cover letter; that is, this proposal letter will be prepared carefully and politely, then submitted to the marriage committee and then will be given to the

⁶ Interview with Parhan, Alumni of the wedding of al Ashriyyah Islamic boarding school students Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

⁷ Interview with Ismail, Alumni of the wedding of al Ashriyyah Islamic boarding school students Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

prospective woman or the prospective partner's family. This cover letter will contain an introduction, complete biodata of the party who submitted the proposal, as well as goals and expectations for establishing a marriage relationship with the prospective partner.⁸

Fourth, waiting for an answer from the prospective partner's family; that is, this process requires patience, because of the time it takes to get an answer from the woman and there is usually deliberation in advance regarding considerations that depend on the policies and family habits of the prospective partner.⁹

Fifth, if the answer from the prospective spouse is positive, the next stage is to come to the candidate's house. Usually, both parties will meet in person at the prospective couple's home to talk more about wedding plans. This meeting became an important moment to strengthen relations between both parties and their families.¹⁰

Sixth, after meeting at the house of the prospective couple, the stage of *taarufan* of the bride and groom is carried out. This is a meeting of the bride and groom which is usually guided by elders or community leaders in *pesantren*. In this stage, we will discuss in more detail about wedding preparation, such as dowry, dowry, wedding procedures, and various other related matters.¹¹

Seventh, after all the preparations are made, both parties will determine the appropriate marriage contract schedule to be carried out. The determination of this schedule usually involves various considerations, including the availability of a place and time agreed upon by both parties and their families.¹²

Eighth, the last stage is the execution of the marriage contract in the presence of witnesses and other related parties. *Akad nikah* is a sacred moment that marks the official start of the marriage bond between the bride and groom, as well as being the culmination

⁸ Interview with Mustakim, Alumni of the wedding of al Ashriyyah Islamic boarding school students Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

⁹ Interview with Asrori, Alumni of the wedding of al Ashriyyah Islamic boarding school students Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

¹⁰ Interview with Saefuddin, Alumni of the wedding of al Ashriyyah Islamic boarding school students Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

¹¹ Interview with Parhan, Alumni of the wedding of al Ashriyyah Islamic boarding school students Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

¹² Interview with Humaidi, Alumni of the wedding of al Ashriyyah Islamic boarding school students Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

of the entire endogamous process among students at the Al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Islamic boarding school in Bogor.¹³

Thus, the process of endogamous marriage among students of pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman, Parung Bogor, shows a commitment to follow the simple and unburdensome teachings of Islam, and prioritize the essence of the marriage itself. This reflects the spirit to carry out religious teachings with simplicity and sincerity, which are values that are upheld in the pesantren environment.

3.2 Endogamous Marriage Model Among Santeri at Pesantren Al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman

Islamic boarding schools have become an alternative choice for some people in looking for potential life partners, especially prospective wives. This is due to the pesantren environment that provides religious education as well as the values of simplicity, independence, discipline, worship, and obedience to the rules of the pesantren.(Al-Amruzi & Faralita, 2022) In pesantren, association with the opposite sex is closely guarded and the use of gadgets is generally prohibited, thus creating an environment conducive to the formation of Islamic character and values.(Fairuzah et al., 2021)

Endomy marriage among students of Al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School Parung Bogor is one of the traditions that is upheld. This wedding is highly recommended for all students who spend their time in the pesantren. The students have the initiative to conduct endogamous marriages with couples who also come from the pesantren environment, both santri and santriwati. They were inspired by figures such as Habib Saggaf bin Mahdi and Umi Waheedah, who were regarded as highly respected role models within the pesantren.(Redaksi Al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman, 2024)

In addition, the harmony of the household lived by Habib Saggaf bin Mahdi and Umi Waheedah, as well as the households of married pesantren alumni, became an inspiration for the students. They see how a home life based on religious values, modesty, and adherence to Islamic teachings can bring blessings and happiness. Thus, this fosters the desire and hope of the students to have a household that is as harmonious and as an example they admire.Editor of Al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman.

¹³ Interview with Abdul Jalil, Daily Administrator of pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

Endomy marriage among Al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor students has been a strong tradition since Habib's time as the leader of the pesantren. He recommended that marriages be performed in huts and between students. In pesantren doctrine, if a teacher or leader gives an exhortation or command to do something, it is considered a sacred command that must be carried out.¹⁴

The teacher's edict is considered a form of command that has spiritual power and is believed to bring blessings in life. Therefore, the recommendation to perform endogamous marriage in accordance with the direction of the Habib becomes an obligation that is considered very important to be obeyed by the students. They believe that carrying out the orders or advice of the pesantren leaders will bring blessings and blessings in their lives, both in this world and in the hereafter.

The tradition of endogamous marriage among Al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor students is not only a habit, but also part of beliefs and teachings that are believed to bring goodness and glory to the perpetrators. This shows the strong influence of pesantren leaders in shaping habits and social norms within the pesantren environment.¹⁵

The tradition of following kyai in the concept of marriage at Pondok Pesantren al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor has a significant impact in tactical coaching and direction to brides-to-be to mature attitudes and thoughts in married life. It also plays a role in the formation of a culture of ta'dzim culture and mutual respect among religious-based communities in Indonesia. The importance of ta'dzim to kyai in the formation of marriage patterns following kyai is a reflection of the majority of students, where they prioritize the orders of the teacher. (Abdillah & Maskuri, 2022) The credibility of the kyai in this regard takes precedence, which includes extensive knowledge and wisdom in various aspects of life including in terms of marriage.

Respect for kyai, especially for students, has a very important value. Apart from being a form of respect, there is also an element of fear associated with this concept. Fear of tools, or disaster for disobeying the kyai's orders, is what underlies this ta'dzim attitude. This creates an atmosphere where disobeying the kyai's orders is considered an act that has the potential to bring misery to students.

¹⁴ Interview with Abdul Jalil, Daily Administrator of pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

¹⁵ Interview with Ali Mutakin, Daily Administrator of pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

Thus, the tradition of following kyai in the concept of marriage is not only about mechanical fulfillment of orders, but also about building relationships full of honor, healthy fear, and awareness of the consequences of actions taken. This reflects a deep appreciation for the spiritual authority and knowledge of the kyai in guiding married life for the student community.

Table 1.

Comparison of Sociological and Psychological Effects of Endogamous Marriage Among Santri

No	Aspects	Effects of Sociology	Psychological Effects
1	Status Sentry	Student data will be enshrined in Pesantren	Feel comfortable and confident
2	Children born	Children from marriages can be traditionally schooled in pesantren	Feel confident because of marrying fellow students
3	Communication with other students	Glorifying each other among the santry	Self-esteem and dignity have been preserved

From this analysis, it can be concluded that endogamous marriage among al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor students has a significant impact both sociologically and psychologically:

1. Sociological; Endogamous marriages strengthen the social structure and identity of pesantren. Student data enshrined in pesantren strengthens the sustainability of the pesantren community, creating consistency and stability in the social structure. Children of endogamous marriages tend to inherit the values and traditions of pesantren for generations, which strengthens social bonds among generations of pesantren.¹⁶

¹⁶ Interview with Abdul Jalil, Daily Administrator of pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

2. Psychological; Endogamous marriages provide a sense of comfort and confidence for students. They feel more valued and recognized by fellow students for choosing a partner from the same environment. This indirectly strengthens their self-esteem and dignity. Children of endogamous marriages also feel confident because having an identity closely linked to pesantren, increasing their sense of pride and psychological well-being.¹⁷

Thus, endogamous marriage among santri al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor not only affects the social structure of pesantren but also has a positive impact on the psychological well-being of individuals and the stability of community identity.

3.3. Endogamous Marriage Among Santeri Sociological Perspectives of Islamic Law

The principle of equality or *kafā'ah* in marriage has a strong strength among the santri al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman. For them, the importance of *kafā'ah* is not only as a social rule, but also as part of the preservation of the teachings of the kyai and the safeguarding of the family from discomfort in their inner circle. This principle is considered a form of protection for the values of pesantren and the sustainability of the student generation.(Amna, 2018)

In the context of *maqāsid ash-Shari'ah*, the exhortation to marry within the circle of santrian is considered to have benefits (*maslāhat*),(Haryanti & Fakhriyah, 2021) especially in maintaining offspring (*hifzu an-nasal*). The principle of *kafā'ah* in terms of santri is considered as an effort to minimize the potential for conflict and quarrels in the family, because it is considered that equality in the line of santri can build a stronger foundation in the household.(Paryadi & Darussamin, 2022)

The majority of students agree with endogamous marriage because they believe that equality in the line of santri is fundamental in building harmonious relationships and strengthening the values taught in pesantren.(Pohan & Nurdin, 2020) A prudent and responsible approach to establishing marriage equality among santri is considered important to ensure that the principle of *kafā'ah* can provide good benefits for individuals and their families, as well as to maintain the continuity of pesantren teachings. The following interview results reinforce this data.

¹⁷ Interview with Ali Mutakin, Daily Administrator of pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

The majority of students support endogamous marriage because they believe that equality along the line of santri is an important foundation in building harmonious relationships and strengthening the values taught in pesantren. For them, marriage within the pesantren environment is not only a means to establish family ties, but also as a way to strengthen solidarity and identity as part of the santri community.¹⁸

Although marriage among students is highly recommended, parents at pesantren al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor do not always force their children to marry fellow students if their soul mate has not come. Parents will usually still give permission to marry their children on the condition that their prospective spouse is also a student or has attended education at a pesantren. If there is no suitable potential partner from among the students, then parents will consider other options as the last alternative.¹⁹

This shows that although there is a drive to maintain equality in the line of civility and strengthen relationships within the pesantren community through endogamous marriage, parents also understand that other factors such as punctuality and conformity in personal characteristics are also important in determining their children's soul mate. This decision reflects a prudent and responsible approach in considering the interests and well-being of their children. Nevertheless, preference is still given to prospective couples who have a polite background, because this is considered to facilitate adaptation and strengthen the values taught in pesantren in married life.

For clarity, responses to this kind of endogamous marriage are shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2.
Response to the marriage of students with santriwati

No	Response	Explanation
1	Family Remains Harmonious	The testimony of the majority of married students at Pesantren al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor living happily, accepting each other with simplicity, not demanding each other, and living a home life in accordance with the vision and mission of their kyai is

¹⁸ Interview with Siti Hafidzah, Daily Administrator of al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung women's boarding school, Bogor, 2024.

¹⁹ Interview with Afif Faijin, Alumnus of Al Ashriya Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

		proof of the success of the education they receive at the pesantren.
2	Divorced Families	Marriage at Pesantren al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor has a very low divorce rate. The majority of married couples in these pesantren manage to maintain their relationships well, creating a strong and harmonious family. Divorces that occur among students in these pesantren are rarely caused by economic factors. Instead, it is more often caused by other factors, such as an accident or illness that causes one partner to die.

From table 2 above, it shows that the response to the marriage of santriwan with santriwati at Pesantren al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor is that the pesantren succeeded in creating an environment that supports the formation of a whole and harmonious family among students. The majority of married couples in this pesantren live happily, accept each other with simplicity, and live a domestic life in accordance with religious teachings and pesantren values.(Pohan & Nurdin, 2020)

The low divorce rate in this pesantren indicates the success of the pesantren in forming a strong and stable relationship among students, although there is a possibility of divorce caused by unexpected factors such as accidents or fatal diseases. However, economic factors are not the main cause of divorce in this pesantren. Overall, the education and environment at Pesantren al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor provide a solid foundation for the formation of harmonious families among students, which is in accordance with the vision and mission of their kyai as well as the Islamic values taught in the pesantren.(Izzi et al., 2021)

Education in pesantren is not only limited to religious doctrine, but also involves character building and the practice of religious values in daily life. At Pesantren al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor, students are not only taught religious theory, but also taught how to apply these religious values in daily practice. Some of these values include: living simply, feeling enough with what's there, being patient with exams, being grateful, etc.²⁰

²⁰ Interview with Ali Mutakin, Daily Administrator of pesantren al Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung, Bogor, 2024.

Most of the students at Pesantren al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor hold the commitment and principle to marry fellow students. This shows that they prioritize the values and identity of pesantren in choosing a life partner. This commitment is reflected in their belief that marrying fellow students can strengthen harmonious relationships, strengthen the values taught in pesantren, and maintain the sustainability of the student community.

By choosing a life partner from among fellow students, they consider that the similarity of background and understanding of religious teachings will facilitate adaptation and communication in the household. In addition, marrying a fellow student is also considered a form of support for the vision and mission of the pesantren and as an effort to maintain the unity and integrity of the pesantren community. This commitment reflects the strength of solidarity and strong identity among al-Ashriyyah Nurul Iman Parung Bogor students, as well as their commitment to live a life based on the values taught in pesantren.

4. Conclusion

The practice of endogamous marriage is one of the important foundations in maintaining the integrity and sustainability of the student community. The main objective is to preserve and maintain harmonious relationships among fellow students, while strengthening the values taught in the pesantren environment. Endogamous marriage is also considered as a means to maintain the identity of the pesantren and ensure the continuity of the generation of santri who will continue to inherit the values of the pesantren which are believed to be the spiritual and moral foundation. Thus, this practice is not only part of the pesantren culture, but also a real effort in maintaining the integrity and sustainability of the santri community in achieving the educational and spiritual goals carried by the pesantren.

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